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Shiksha Shodh Manthan

A Half Yearly International Peer-Reviewed Refereed Journal of Education

Index

A Study of Human Rights Understanding among Students at Higher Level Dr. Kshama Pandey & Prof. Anil shukla kshamasoham@gmail.com	1
Encouraging Environment of Environmental Education in India Dr. Amit Kumar Dr_amitsharma08@rediffmail.com	6
Ethics and Values Inculcation among Future-Teachers Dr. Kirti Prajapati, Dr. Arpana Godbole & Dr. Rochana Shukla keertiprajapati@gmail.com	13
Study of Value conflict among Under graduate Students of Different gender and locality of Bareilly District Dr. Pratibha Sharma & Mrs. Shivi Agarwal Shiviag13@gmail.com	19
A Study of Value Patterns Among Primary School Teachers Prof. Reena Agarwal & Ashish kumar Sharma Aks14281@gmail.com	25
Impact of M- Learning on Social Presence Rekha Kashyap & Prof. Dinesh Kumar rekhagsr1986@gmail.com	37
Legal Education in India : An Overview Dr. Mahesh Laxmanrao Dharmapurikar Maheshld2012@yahoo.com	43
The Use of Bloom Taxonomy to Develop Higher Order Thinking Skills in Students Soniya Yadav Soniayadhuvanshi98@gmail.com	48
Child Labour in India: Impact of Right to Education, Offences and Punishment Mukesh Kumar & Dr. Gulab Chandra Rai M.kumarlaw1984@gmail.com	54
Impact of Inductive Thinking Model and ICT based Teaching on Commercial Understanding of Higher Secondary Students Megha Gangwar & Prof. Sarnath Singh Gangwar.megha84@gmail.com	61

7/209

Shiksha Shodh Manthan

Vol.6, No.2, October 2020

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A Half Yearly International Peer-Reviewed Refereed Journal of Education

Universal Design for Learning (UDL): A Tools for Inclusive Setting Mr. Dhananjay Bharti & Dr. Chhaya Soni Dhananjaybharti.bhu@gmail.com	66
New Education Policy (NEP) Shaifali Agarwal Akshato2agarwal@gmail.com	75
Role of Protection Officer under the Domestic Violence Act, 2005 Sahnaz Akhtar	81

The Use of Bloom Taxonomy to Develop Higher Order Thinking Skills in Students

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Abstract

The present paper aimed to develop the relation between Bloom Taxonomy (Cognitive Domain) and Higher Order Thinking Skills. Basically, cognitive domain classification started with objective: Knowledge, Understanding, Application, Analysis, Synthesis and Evaluation. But Higher Order Thinking skills reflected by the top three levels in Bloom's Taxonomy: analysis, synthesis, and evaluation. When the researcher develop the relation between Bloom Taxonomy and thinking skills, on the basis of that it can be said that taxonomy divided into two parts LOTS and HOTS. LOTS is started with Knowledge, Understanding objectives. And HOTS started with Apply, Analysis, Synthesis and reach the highest level of objective evaluate. So, it's said that the lower-order thinking skills (LOTS) involve, remembering, memorization and conceptualization. And HOTS involve apply, analysis, synthesis and evaluation. So, objective of the paper is creating the relationship between Bloom taxonomy cognitive domain and higher order thinking skills.

Keywords: Bloom Taxonomy, Higher Order Thinking Skills (HOTS), Lower Order Thinking Skills (LOTS).

Introduction :

Education is the most powerful weapon which you can use to change the world.

..... Nelson Mandela.

Education is one of the important aspects that can affect national vision and success in educational implementation is a key to a better future but this future depend on today educational policy, learning environment and thinking skills. We have most of skills for students to create a healthy environment for learning but its need to implementation of these skills in classroom setting. If we overview from ancient to modern era our education system faces many changes, for example in ancient time rote method is used in learning, its approximate same in Muslim time, but after that as psychological technique is used in education field than after a new and good changes is highlighted in educational field. Through these technique learning environment is enriched, because of its able to train students to think innovative, creative and critically.

Higher-order thinking skills (HOTS) is a favored concept in American education. It differentiate critical thinking skills from low-order learning outcomes, functioning as those attained by

remembering, recall and memorization. According to Lewis & Smith, 1993 Higher order thinking skills include problem solving, critical thinking, decision making, and creative thinking. Thinking does not occur spontaneously but must be "evoked" by "problems and questions" or by "some perplexity, confusion or doubt (Dewey 1933)". It's important to teach students to think about their own thinking processes (Kauchak & Eggen, 1998). Higher order thinking skills include critical, logical, reflective, meta-cognitive and creative thinking. According to King (1997), the ability of higher order thinking skills are activated when individuals encounter unfamiliar problems, uncertainties, questions and dilemmas. When these skills are nurtured and well developed, one can perform better during explanations and making decisions as well as grow their intellectual skills. Development of higher order thinking skills, relies on their lower level thinking skills thus making higher order thinking skills grounded with lower level thinking